

Supplementary Data: Model-based Bayesian inference of the ventilation distribution in patients with Cystic Fibrosis from multiple breath washout, with comparison to ventilation MRI

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Figure S1: Effect of MBW down-sampling parameters

We generated artificial MBW data using realisations of the compartmental lung model with different values of σ_V . Data was generated using a model with $V_0 = 3L$, $V_D = 200ml$ and $\sigma_V = \{0.3, 0.5, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0\}$, and the tidal volume used was assumed to be a periodic step function with period 5s (2.5s inhalation and 2.5s exhalation). The tidal volumes were generated uniformly at random within the range 0.72 to 1.08L, to simulate variations in breath volume. Measurements (with simulated measurement error as described in the text) were generated for 10ms intervals and these were then outputted to match the format of the raw MBW measurements from experiments. These were then processed and fitted with the same method outlined in the main paper, but the values of N_{II} and N_{III} (the number of sample points used to represent phase-II and III) were varied. We set $N_{II} = N_{III}$ here to reduce the parameter space, and note that $N_{II} + N_{III} = 8$ is the value used throughout the main paper. (a) – (c) shows the posterior predicted parameters for V_0 , V_D , and σ_V respectively as we change the number of sample points. Evidently there is very little change in the parameters recovered for $N_{II} + N_{III} \geq 12$, and our choice of $N_{II} + N_{III} = 8$ appears to recover the parameters well with similar uncertainty to the highest sampling-rate tested ($N_{II} + N_{III} = 40$). The different markers represent fits to data generated using the σ_V values listed in the legend, and the dashed lines indicate the actual parameters used to generate the data. The y-axis range is set to match the range of the model priors, and the error bars indicate the 95% prediction interval.

Figure S2: Effect of number of model compartments

We generated artificial MBW data using realisations of the compartmental lung model with 500 compartments ($N_c = 500$), using the same parameters and methods as outlined in figure S2. (a) – (c) shows the posterior predicted parameters for V_0 , V_D , and σ_V respectively as we change the number of compartments in the fitting model. It is clear that as N_c is increased, parameter uncertainty decreases. In the paper we use $N_c = 50$ as a balance between execution time and reducing unnecessary uncertainty. The different markers represent fits to data generated using the σ_V values listed in the legend, and the dashed lines indicate the actual parameters used to generate the data. The y-axis range is set to match the range of the model priors, and the error bars indicate the 95% prediction interval.

Figure S3: Agreement of physiological model parameters and pulmonary function measurements

Comparison of model parameters and MBW counterparts. (a) Model (blue) and MBW (orange) measured FRC vs. FRC measured via plethysmography. (b) Model dead-space versus MBW measured Fowler dead-space (measured from CO₂ trace). (c) Model VH parameter σ_V vs. LCI. Key: MAP = Maximum a posteriori (most likely measurement value from ABC-SMC algorithm), IQR = Interquartile range (central 50% of sampled posterior distribution from ABC-SMC algorithm), 95% range (central 95% of sampled posterior distribution from ABC-SMC), LOA = limits of agreement (2 standard deviations either side of the mean), and MBW S.D. is the standard deviation of all MBW test repeats performed.

Figures S2(a) and (b) show that the parameters V_0 and V_D agree well with the MBW measured values V_{FRC} and V_{FDS} in the majority of cases. Figure S2(c) shows that there is strong correlation between the VH parameter σ_V and LCI measured by MBW. In figure S2(a), it is also shown that model inferred FRC values (V_0) correlate and agree more closely with plethysmography measurement than MBW measured FRC volumes (V_{FRC}) do.

Figure S4: Relationship between inferred parameters

Significant parameter interdependence is observed in the model predictions. (a) The relative difference between predicted FRC volume and that measured by MBW vs. the ventilation heterogeneity parameter σ_V . (b) The relative difference between predicted dead-space volume and Fowler dead-space measured by MBW vs. the ventilation heterogeneity parameter σ_V . (c) The inter-quartile range (IQR) of the parameter σ_V (a measure of the uncertainty) vs. the maximum a posteriori (MAP) value (i.e. the predicted value). The 95% range in plots (a) and (b) shows the limits of the central 95% of the posterior distribution for each parameter (the error in MBW measured quantities is not included in the error bars as there are insufficient experimental samples to determine the IQR or 95% range for these).

Figure S3(a) shows that increased ventilation heterogeneity σ_V results in an increase of the fitted FRC volume (V_0) relative to the value directly computed by MBW. This is to be expected because as σ_V becomes large more lung volume becomes so poorly ventilated that inert gas contained in these regions remains effectively trapped for the model duration. Therefore, while the resultant gas trace may match the MBW measurements closely, the total inert gas exhaled is not proportional to the model FRC volume and so will be larger than that calculated by MBW.

Table S1: Predicted Ventilation Distributions

For each subject, the predicted distribution (figure 4 of main text) was calculated by taking the simulated MR distribution from each accepted realisation and generating a histogram with even bin-spacing h for each one. The average distribution is then constructed as the median frequency for each bin, where the medians are taken from all of the accepted realisations in the final generation of the ABC-SMC algorithm. The uncertainty in predictions is dependent on the desired precision used to characterise the distribution. We used $h = 0.16$ spaced bins for the distribution measured by imaging and the distribution predicted by modelling.

Accuracy of prediction was quantified by comparing the median predicted cumulative distribution functions (CDFs) of the image intensity to those measured (note this does not depend on the bin-spacing h). To do this we computed the root-mean-squared residuals δ_{RMSE} of the predicted CDF against that measured for each individual. We also computed the Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) statistic δ_{KS} for the two curves, defined as the maximum distance between them. In both cases this was computed by sampling each CDF at the same 1000 evenly spaced intervals. The former is a measure of the average distance between the curves (where, by their nature, the CDF functions are constrained between 0 and 1), whereas the latter is a measure of the distance between them at their point of worst agreement. To put these into context, the same measures were also computed for

D1. A simple lognormal fit to the actual observed MRI data: We used a lognormal function with fixed unit mean (of the form in equation (S2)). To perform this, we used the maximum likelihood estimation function in matlab with an initial guess of $\sigma_V = 0.6$.

D2. A “null” hypothesis: The median intensity distribution predicted by the model priors (from randomly generated parameters sets).

	δ_{RMSE}	δ_{KS}
Median model posterior	0.040 (0.017)	0.113 (0.065)
Mean model posterior	0.040 (0.017)	0.112 (0.064)
D1) Lognormal fit	0.070 (0.037)	0.156 (0.069)
D2) Median model prior	0.156 (0.069)	0.342 (0.062)

The results are given above as the mean (s.d.) of the whole dataset. They show that the model posterior predictions (whether using the mean or median) were better than both, confirming that not only does the model fit much better than random (case D2), it also fits the measured data better than a single parameter distribution fitted to the measured data itself (case D1). Taken together this supports that the model has good predictive value.

Figure S5: Role of acinar mixing in model fitting error

Figure S5 shows the correlation between the measured S_{acin} (\pm s.d. from MBW repeats), the MRI goodness-of-fit (as measured by the Kolmogorov-Smirnov statistic between the MRI-observed ventilation distribution and that predicted by the median model fit), and the MBW goodness-of-fit (as measured by root-mean-squared-error between the measured MBW concentration and the median model fit). (a) S_{acin} vs. MBW goodness-of-fit, (b) S_{acin} vs. MRI goodness-of-fit, and (c) MBW goodness-of-fit vs. MRI goodness-of-fit. For each case we show the least-squares linear fit with Pearson r and p -values given in the insets. The significant correlation in all figures suggests that the model-fitting error is affected by acinar mixing, whether measured by the goodness-of-fit to the MBW data, or the resulting MRI prediction. Note that for both of these goodness-of-fit measures, a lower value is better.

Figure S6: Example fitted MBW traces

Two examples of fitted MBW traces corresponding to the patients in figures 6(b) and 6(u) respectively (i.e. the best and worst fits to the MRI data respectively). Datapoints fitted to are plotted on a log scale, the fitted line indicates the median model fit, while the shaded region is the 95% confidence interval.

Figure S7: Outlier cases and sources of disagreement

There are a few cases where the model predicted ventilation distribution qualitatively differs from that measured by MRI. To investigate these further we looked at the raw images to see if there was a clue as to why this was difficult to fit. A key example is given in figure 6(k), where the model prediction completely misses the spike at very low specific ventilation. The figure below shows the masked image for this case (top row axial, coronal and sagittal slices from left to right), and also highlights the unventilated fraction (bottom row, same images with ventilated regions in yellow and unventilated in red). We can clearly see that the right-upper lobe (left-hand-side of coronal slice image) is barely ventilated, and that the cut-off and the lobar boundary is very clear. This suggests a proximal airway is almost completely blocked, cutting off most of this lobe from the rest of the lung, and making it hard to detect via MBW. This highlights a shortcoming of this particular model, and MBW more generally, in its inability to detect regions with extremely low specific ventilation, since, by definition, they do not contribute much to the inert gas signal during washout.

